

THE VALUE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF FEEDBACK IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' LEARNING.

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Annotation: This article comes with some modern and technology based way of providing feedback which can eventually help students in improving student learning experience.

Key words: effective feedback, positive feedback, improve students' learning

Feedback is any response regarding a student's performance or behavior. It can be verbal, written or gestural. The purpose of feedback in the assessment and learning process is to improve a student's performance - not put a damper on it. It is essential that the process of providing feedback is a positive, or at least a neutral, learning experience for the student. Negative feedback can discourage student effort and achievement. Instructors have the distinct responsibility to nurture a student's learning and to provide feedback in such a manner that the student does not leave the classroom feeling defeated. Feedback is designed to bring about an improvement in learners' performance and achievement. Feedback can be given by the practitioner or by peers. It can be either formal or informal. It can be oral or written, it can be formative or summative, but overall it must provide the learner with specific advice on how to improve their performance. The process of giving feedback begins with the practitioner and learner clarifying the learning intentions (or goals) for the activities they are undertaking and the success criteria by which they will assess the level of achievement to be demonstrated by learners. This enables the learners to measure their performance in terms of both mastery of the set task and the processes inherent in it. It also helps them to be clear about future

goals. Good feedback practice can not only provide useful information to the students in improving their learning, but also can offer decent information to teachers which is eventually improve the learning experience for the students. While producing relevant and informative feedback in meeting the students' demand, the teachers themselves need to have fair idea about the students' progression. They eventually become more involved in reviewing and reflecting on students' performance which drives them to make better learning environment. At the time of providing feedback it is important that after reading that a student should have a positive feeling about that feedback. This is considered as a process of motivating the students to utilise the feedback they have received. Feedback should not be discouraging the students at any cost. Obviously, it is vital to draw the student's attention to the less successful parts of a coursework, however the teachers should be cautious in providing "negative feedback" of this kind. Thus teachers can improve students' learning environment by presenting the feedback in a positive way. Feedback needs to be timely. It needs to be given while there is still time for the learners to act on it and to monitor and adjust their learning.

It can be 'in-the-moment' in the case of classroom dialogue and discussion. The practitioner will receive feedback from the way learners answer questions and the questions asked by them. To effectively gather evidence from questioning about who does and who does not understand it may be necessary to vary the way, questions are asked in the classroom to ensure all learners can participate and provide evidence of their level of understanding. This evidence should indicate whether it is necessary to reteach, provide more varied discussion and practice, use peer teaching or move the learners forward.

Feedback on formal tasks that just include marks or grades or comments that discuss the level of performance and suggest that the learning journey is finished should be avoided. This can prevent the learner from fully considering and acting on the feedback. Multiple forms of feedback, such as comments, questions, and

discussion provided frequently during learning encourage engagement and motivation to succeed.

There are some tips for giving effective feedback to learners

- Explain to the learners that you are focusing on helping them to understand the assessment of their learning
- Encourage learners to ask questions about their feedback
- Make a regular time to discuss feedback with learners on an individual or small group basis
- Advise learners that they will have an opportunity to ask questions about their assessment
- Encourage them to note down their questions
- Try to give feedback as close to the learning and assessment task as possible
- Be specific and explicit about feedback, providing examples where possible
- Establish that the student understands what is being discussed
- Ask the student what they think they need to improve on
- Offer your advice about future steps for improvement
- Invite conversations by asking learners to discuss the work with you and/or with their peers

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